

Vector Tracking Loop Jitter

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Abstract

The vector architecture is an advanced signal tracking algorithm of global navigation satellite system (GNSS) receivers. It has long been the subject of much research for its ability to deal with GNSS vulnerability. This paper presents a methodology to find the total jitter of the non-coherent vector tracking architecture using its state space (SS) formulation, referred to as SS jitter, and relates it to that determined with transfer function (TF) models. Thus, a theoretical framework for evaluating the performance of non-coherent vector loops is developed. In this regard, vector TFs are derived in the z-domain without decoupling the delay and frequency locked loops, unlike previous work. Two different noise equivalent bandwidths from the z-domain TF are also calculated. A close agreement between the SS and TF jitters is demonstrated, proving their equivalence. A metric to represent the collective performance of vector loops for loss of lock detection is identified using dynamically allocated bounds on the jitter. Steady state jitter performance at different noise levels in the absence of dynamic stress error is analyzed in detail. Finally, using high dynamic simulations of the global positioning system and navigation with Indian constellation signals, it is illustrated that the proposed metric holds promise for detecting loss of lock in the presence of jerk.

Keywords

Vector Tracking Loops, State Space Jitter, Transfer Function Jitter, Noise Equivalent Bandwidth, Loss of Lock

1 | INTRODUCTION

The vector tracking architecture is an advanced receiver algorithm developed to address the vulnerability of global navigation satellite system (GNSS) signals (Spilker Jr., 1995). Since its introduction in the 1980s (Copps et al., 1980), extensive research has been carried out to explore its potential for improving GNSS robustness against signal degradation, signal outages, and high platform dynamics (Lashley et al., 2009). Different variants of this tracking method with enhanced capabilities are also proposed in the literature. They include joint vector tracking (Liu et al., 2011), maximum likelihood vector architecture (Weill, 2010), differential vector phase locked loop (Brewer & Raquet, 2016), and multi-receiver vector tracking (Ng & Gao, 2017). The superiority of the vector receiver over the traditional scalar one, however, comes with the price of increased computational complexities. Recent work is, therefore, directed toward reducing its computational load without sacrificing the performance much (Mu & Long, 2017; Abedi & Mosavi, 2022; Gómez et al., 2023), thus paving the way for real-time vector loop implementations.

Multi-GNSS vector tracking receivers have also been studied in the literature for better performance (Shytermeja, 2017; Tabatabaei et al., 2017).

Traditionally, the performance of designed scalar tracking loop architectures is quantitatively evaluated by its total jitter (Ward et al., 2006). It is given by the sum of the $3\text{-}\sigma$ tracking error due to wideband and colored noises and dynamic stress error arising from abrupt changes in platform motion. In Ward et al., 2006, different sources of jitter are studied in detail for both conventional phase and frequency locked loops using appropriate transfer function (TF) models. With the help of the total jitter, Razavi et al., 2008 explain the relative importance of different tracking parameters on systematically designing a scalar loop. It is also shown that jitter is a reliable metric for loss of lock detection if the scalar tracking loop bandwidth (BW) is not much small. Yang et al., 2017 and Mute and Bhattacharyya, 2023 analyze how the tracking loop jitter varies in adaptive scalar loops, whose parameters are adaptively chosen based on carrier to noise ratios (C/N_0) and platform dynamics (or line of sight jerk).

While the jitter of a scalar tracking loop is well-studied, a similar treatment is lacking in the context of more complex vector architecture. Lashley et al., 2009 provide a methodology to calculate the vector jitter considering thermal noise, clock noise and dynamic stress error for a non-coherent vector loop with 20 ms measurement update intervals. In the presented approach, the calculation of jitter due to noise involves updating the state error covariance using a two-step process. The dynamic stress error is shown to be derived from the state error difference between two separate Kalman filters, of which one has the knowledge of dynamics and, therefore, accurately models the change in acceleration, and the other does not. As channels are coupled in vector tracking mode, the maximum jitter among all channels is compared against the threshold for loss of lock analysis. Simulation results depict that during a 8g maneuver at 16 dB-Hz, the velocity estimates of the vector loops start to diverge. The jitters of the majority of channels also exceed the threshold, thereby correctly predicting loss of lock. However, the performance is not validated at different carrier to noise ratios (C/N_0 s) against specific platform jerk levels. In order to find the vector loop jitter with TF models similar to that of its scalar counterpart, appropriate TFs of the time-varying vector tracking architecture are needed. While Bhattacharyya, 2018 describes s-domain TF models and noise equivalent BWs of vector loops under certain assumptions, to the best of the author's knowledge, there is hardly any work on vector jitter calculation using TFs.

This paper determines the total jitter of a non-coherent vector architecture with both state space (SS) and TF formulations. Major contributions of the work are as follows. First, a theoretical framework for evaluating the performance of vector loops is presented in terms of the SS- and TF-based tracking jitters. More precisely, the *a priori* and *a posteriori* jitters based on the theoretical SS model called SS jitters are obtained. Then, z-domain TF models of the vector loops are determined without decoupling the delay and frequency locked loops, unlike Bhattacharyya, 2018. The current TF formulation removes all other key assumptions of the previous work, is more generic in nature, and has a much simpler implementation. Two different noise equivalent BWs one each for measurement noise and process noise are also calculated. A close agreement between the SS and TF jitters is established to show their equivalence. Second, with the help of the SS jitter, a practical loss of lock detection algorithm is developed for the non-coherent vector loops. The SS jitters are initially obtained at the measurement update intervals. To reduce the computational load, the measurement updates of the non-coherent vector loops are often performed at an interval higher than the coherent integration time, which is usually 10 ms for carrier frequency tracking and 20 ms for code phase (Bhattacharyya & Gebre-Egziabher, 2010). Therefore, intermediate bounds on the jitter are calculated every 20 ms in order to apply existing

thresholds for loss of lock detection. A suitable metric for representing the collective performance of all channels is also identified. The proposed metric is used to detect loss of lock in the presence of jerk in a high dynamic simulation. It should be noted that simulations are performed with the global positioning system (GPS) L1 and navigation with Indian constellation (NavIC) L5 signals. Thus, geometric as well as frequency diversities are attained in a single scenario, which demonstrates the effectiveness of the methodology for different constellations as well as different signals.

The remaining paper is organized as follows. First, the approach to calculating the SS jitter is described. Then, TF models are introduced and noise equivalent BWs are determined. Using this, the TF jitter is obtained. Following this, an appropriate metric is proposed for loss of lock detection with the help of the SS jitter. Next, simulation studies illustrate the equivalence between the SS and TF jitters, and study vector jitter performance at different noise and jerk levels. Finally, conclusions are provided.

FIGURE 1 Non-coherent vector loop architecture. Appropriate variables at the channel and navigation levels are indicated in the figure.

f_{code} and $f_{carr}^{G/N}$ are the code chipping rate and GPS/NavIC carrier frequency, respectively, and c is the speed of light

2 | VECTOR LOOP JITTER

In this paper, a non-coherent vector tracking architecture is considered for GPS and NavIC constellations (see Figure 1) to find the vector loop jitter. It consists of vector delay locked loops (VDLL) for code phase tracking and vector frequency locked loops (VFLL) for carrier frequency tracking. The state transition and linearized measurement models of the vector navigation filter, which uses an extended Kalman filter (EKF) implementation, are as follows.

$$\underline{z}_\ell = \mathbf{F} \underline{z}_{\ell-1} + \underline{w}_{\ell-1} \quad (1)$$

$$\underline{z}_\ell = \mathbf{H}_\ell \Delta \underline{z}_\ell + \underline{\zeta}_\ell \quad (2)$$

The vector, $\Delta \underline{z}_\ell$ at t_ℓ , is given by $(\underline{z}_\ell - \hat{\underline{z}}_\ell^-)$. The true state vector is \underline{z}_ℓ , and its *a priori* estimate is $\hat{\underline{z}}_\ell^-$. \underline{z}_ℓ comprises the user position, velocity and acceleration in the Earth-centered Earth fixed (ECEF) coordinate frame, and GPS and NavIC receiver clock biases, drifts and drift rates, and thus, has 15 elements. It should be noted that the position estimation error in ECEF can later be converted to the local navigation frame to compute the vertical and horizontal position errors. In the filter, $\hat{\underline{z}}_\ell^-$ and the *a posteriori* estimate of \underline{z}_ℓ , $\hat{\underline{z}}_\ell^+$, are propagated from a time instant t'_{k-1} to t'_k by multiplying the matrix, \mathbf{F}' , which is

$$\mathbf{F}' = \mathbf{I}_{5 \times 5} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \Delta t' & ((\Delta t')^2)/2 \\ 0 & 1 & \Delta t' \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where \otimes denotes the Kronecker tensor product. $\mathbf{I}_{5 \times 5}$ is the 5×5 identity matrix. t'_k increments every 20 ms. Thus, $\Delta t' = (t'_k - t'_{k-1}) = 20$ ms. The subscript ℓ in Equation 1, on the other hand, indicates the time instants for measurement updates (i.e., t_ℓ). In the implementation of this paper, t_ℓ increments every 0.1 s (i.e. $\Delta t = (t_{\ell+1} - t_\ell) = 0.1$ s). It is apparent that $t_\ell = t'_k$ when $k = 5\ell$ (with $\ell = 1, 2, \dots$). Hence, $\mathbf{F} = (\mathbf{F}')^5$. The process noise vector, $\underline{w}_{\ell-1}$, is assumed to be added to get the true states every t_ℓ , as shown in Equation 1. $\underline{w}_{\ell-1}$ has zero mean and error covariance \mathbf{Q} . \underline{z}_ℓ is the measurement innovation vector at t_ℓ , and $\underline{\zeta}_\ell$ is the measurement noise vector at t_ℓ with zero mean and covariance \mathbf{W}_ℓ . \underline{w} and $\underline{\zeta}$ are unknown vectors; only their statistical properties (i.e., mean and covariance) can be predicted. \underline{z}_ℓ is obtained from five 20-ms code phase (early-minus-late envelope) and carrier frequency (atan2) discriminator outputs averaged over 0.1 s. It should be noted that, before transitioning from scalar to vector loops in the beginning, the coherent integration time of the correlators is synchronized with data bit transitions. The data bit boundaries are continuously tracked afterward by counting twenty 1-ms C/A-code periods. So, the two 10-ms prompt correlator pair intervals of the atan2 carrier frequency discriminator are ensured not to fall across data bit boundaries. The measurement model matrix, \mathbf{H}_ℓ , relates \underline{z}_ℓ to $\Delta \underline{z}_\ell$. It is defined in Appendix 6.1. Interested readers can also refer to the supplementary material of Mute and Bhattacharyya, 2023 for a detailed discussion of the measurement model and code and carrier numerically controlled oscillator corrections of the dual-constellation GPS L1 and NavIC L5 vector tracking architecture.

If \underline{e}_ℓ^+ is the state estimation error after a measurement update (i.e., $\underline{e}_\ell^+ = (\underline{z}_\ell - \hat{\underline{z}}_\ell^+)$), then it can be propagated to the next time step as (Simon, 2006)

$$\underline{e}_{\ell+1}^+ = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_{\ell+1} \mathbf{H}_{\ell+1}) \mathbf{F} \underline{e}_\ell^+ + (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_{\ell+1} \mathbf{H}_{\ell+1}) \underline{w}_\ell - \mathbf{K}_{\ell+1} \underline{\zeta}_{\ell+1} \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{K}_{\ell+1}$ is the Kalman gain at $t_{\ell+1}$. Using Equation 4, the propagation of the *a priori* state error before a measurement update, $\underline{e}_\ell^- (= \Delta \underline{z}_\ell)$, is given as

$$\underline{e}_{\ell+1}^- = (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{K}'_\ell \mathbf{H}_\ell) \underline{e}_\ell^- + \underline{w}_\ell - \mathbf{K}'_\ell \underline{\zeta}_\ell \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{K}'_\ell = \mathbf{F} \mathbf{K}_\ell$. The vector loop jitter is defined separately for the VDLL and VFLL, using the *a priori* and *a posteriori* state estimation errors, $\underline{e}_{\ell+1}^-$ and $\underline{e}_{\ell+1}^+$. This is because the code phase and carrier frequency of a channel are aligned with the incoming ones based on the estimated or predicted state vector of the vector navigation filter, as shown in Figure 1. Therefore, the state estimation/prediction error at the navigation level will reflect as code phase and carrier frequency alignment errors at the channel

level. Hence, the *a posteriori* (and *a priori*) code phase and carrier Doppler errors together can be written as $\underline{\epsilon}_{e, \ell+1} = \mathbf{H}_{\ell+1} \underline{e}_{\ell+1}^+$ (and $\underline{\epsilon}_{p, \ell+1} = \mathbf{H}_{\ell+1} \underline{e}_{\ell+1}^-$). The vectors, $\underline{\epsilon}_{e, \ell+1}$ and $\underline{\epsilon}_{p, \ell+1}$, are of dimension $2n \times 1$, where n is the number of visible satellites used for positioning. The code phase errors are given by the first n elements, and the carrier Doppler errors are obtained from the next n elements. The total *a posteriori* VDLL (or VFLL) jitter of a channel comprises the $3\text{-}\sigma$ *a posteriori* code phase (or carrier Doppler) estimation error due to random effects or noises plus the transient and steady state error due to abrupt changes in platform dynamics (i.e., the dynamic stress error, which is treated as a deterministic quantity). This is an extension of the definition provided by Ward et al., 2006 for scalar tracking loops. Similarly, the total *a priori* jitter is defined. As the vector navigation filter estimates the user position, velocity and acceleration, the dynamic stress error primarily arises from the user jerk. In this paper, the jitter is studied after the initial transients of the navigation filter have died down.

In order to be able to calculate the vector loop jitter for each channel, the effects of the process and measurement noises should be reflected in $\underline{\epsilon}_{e, \ell+1}$ through $\underline{e}_{\ell+1}^+$ (and in $\underline{\epsilon}_{p, \ell+1}$ through $\underline{e}_{\ell+1}^-$). For this purpose, the matrix pair, $(\mathbf{H}_{\ell+1}, (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_{\ell+1} \mathbf{H}_{\ell+1}) \mathbf{F})$ must be observable in case of $\underline{\epsilon}_{e, \ell+1}$, where $\mathbf{H}_{\ell+1}$ is the measurement model matrix and $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_{\ell+1} \mathbf{H}_{\ell+1}) \mathbf{F}$ is the system model matrix (Kailath, 1980). This is proved in Appendix (Section 6.2), assuming $(\mathbf{H}_{\ell+1}, \mathbf{F})$ is observable for a stable vector navigation filter, and \mathbf{F} is invertible (valid for the adopted model). It is also proved that the matrix pairs, $((\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_{\ell+1} \mathbf{H}_{\ell+1}) \mathbf{F}, (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_{\ell+1} \mathbf{H}_{\ell+1}))$ and $((\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_{\ell+1} \mathbf{H}_{\ell+1}) \mathbf{F}, \mathbf{K}_{\ell+1})$, are reachable or stabilizable with regard to the noises, \underline{w}_ℓ and $\underline{\zeta}_{\ell+1}$, for $\underline{e}_{\ell+1}^+$, respectively, where the first matrix of a pair is the system model matrix and the second one is the coefficient matrix for the input vector (see Sections 6.3-6.4 for derivations). It should be noted that the matrix pairs written as before are the standard representations of matrices in control theory for defining the system observability and reachability/stabilizability. While the latter is not essential in their usual sense for jitter calculation, for completeness, the proof in the Appendix justifies that some modes of $\underline{e}_{\ell+1}^+$ are affected by the noises. Hence, $\underline{\epsilon}_{e, \ell+1}$ would reflect the effects of \underline{w}_ℓ and $\underline{\zeta}_{\ell+1}$ on $\underline{e}_{\ell+1}^+$ through observability. The observability of $\underline{\epsilon}_{p, \ell+1}$ is shown as part of the proof in Section 6.2 of the Appendix. The reachability criteria can be easily proved following the approach of the Appendix. Observability and stabilizability will also be assessed in the context of the dynamic stress error later. Next, the mathematical expression of the total SS jitter for vector loops is provided.

2.1 | State Space Jitter

It is shown in Simon, 2006 that for a given Kalman gain matrix, the steady state estimation error covariance can be written as the sum of the covariance due to process noise only and the covariance due to measurement noise only. That is, after the initial transients die down, the estimation error covariance is determined by the process and measurement noises. Therefore, if $\Sigma_{p, \ell}^+$ and $\Sigma_{m, \ell}^+$ denote the *a posteriori* error covariances only for \underline{w} and $\underline{\zeta}$, respectively, then the *a posteriori* error covariance, Σ_ℓ^+ , after the initial transients die down, is $(\Sigma_{p, \ell}^+ + \Sigma_{m, \ell}^+)$. The same can also be written for the *a priori* error covariance, Σ_ℓ^- . Thus, two jitters due to noise (called noise jitters later) can be calculated one each with Σ_ℓ^- and Σ_ℓ^+ . They are called *a priori* and *a posteriori* SS noise jitters, respectively, in this paper. The *a posteriori* SS noise jitter for a channel i in VDLL is given by

$$\sigma_{VDLL_{noise, \ell}^+}^{(i)} = \sqrt{\mathbf{G}_\ell^+(i, i)} \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{G}_\ell^+ = \mathbf{H}_\ell \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\ell^+ \mathbf{H}_\ell^T$, and $i = 1, \dots, n$. n is the number of satellites used for positioning at epoch ℓ , and can change with time. $\sigma_{VDLLnoise, \ell}^+$ represents the VDLL noise jitter vector for all channels whereas its argument denotes the i th channel. For the VFLL

$$\sigma_{VFLLnoise, \ell}^+(\eta) = \sqrt{\mathbf{G}_\ell^+(\eta, \eta)}, \quad \eta = n + 1, \dots, 2n \quad (7)$$

Similarly, with $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\ell^-$, the *a priori* noise jitters for the VDLL and VFLL, respectively, are

$$\sigma_{VDLLnoise, \ell}^-(i) = \sqrt{\mathbf{G}_\ell^-(i, i)} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{VFLLnoise, \ell}^-(\eta) = \sqrt{\mathbf{G}_\ell^-(\eta, \eta)} \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{G}_\ell^- = \mathbf{H}_\ell \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\ell^- \mathbf{H}_\ell^T$. Following the definition after Equation 5, the $1\text{-}\sigma$ total jitter of a channel is given by the sum of the noise jitter and one-third of the dynamic stress error, which separately accounts for the effect of non-zero mean of \underline{w} . It should be noted that \underline{w} is assumed to have zero mean, and its covariance, \mathbf{Q} , is only considered in the noise jitter calculation earlier. As the user acceleration is modeled constant in the vector navigation filter, user jerk will result in a dynamic stress error. In this paper, the final jitter for loss of lock detection is determined later using both *a priori* and *a posteriori* jitters. It should be noted that a separate consideration is made for the contributions of process noise (or \mathbf{Q}) in the jitter and of dynamic stress error arising from jerk. The diagonal elements of \mathbf{Q} corresponding to the user acceleration may have comparatively high values than other elements so that the filter appropriately learns from its measurements during dynamics. But the actual jerk need not be the same as what is expected from \mathbf{Q} . So, the dynamic stress error needs to be included. While considering full \mathbf{Q} in the noise jitter along with the dynamic stress error may result in an overbound of the total jitter, simulation results will show that this does not lead to a false detection of loss of lock. A partial reason is that the contribution of the diagonal acceleration terms of \mathbf{Q} to \mathbf{G}_ℓ^- via the addition of \mathbf{Q} in $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\ell^-$ is zero as the respective columns of \mathbf{H}_ℓ for the acceleration are zero (see Appendix 6.1). Also, considering only the clock part of \mathbf{Q} to separately update the noise jitter in a two-step process following Lashley et al., 2009 would require fairly accurate knowledge of the clock parameters. This may not always be possible, and parameters may change with time. As a conservative approach, full \mathbf{Q} is preferred in this paper to overbound the noise jitter.

The dynamic stress error is calculated at each epoch for a given user jerk profile, instead of finding the steady state error for a constant jerk level. This is to account for a real scenario that jerk need not remain constant and can change with time. The calculation of the dynamic stress error is described next. The *a priori* state error due to non-zero jerk, $\Delta \underline{z}_{dyn, \ell}^-$, before the measurement update at ℓ is

$$\Delta \underline{z}_{dyn, \ell}^- = \mathbf{F} \Delta \underline{z}_{dyn, \ell-1}^+ + \mathbf{B} \underline{u}_{jerk, \ell-1} \quad (9)$$

where $\Delta \underline{z}_{dyn, \ell-1}^+$ is the cumulative state error due to previous jerks after the measurement update at $\ell - 1$, and is a zero vector when $\ell = 1$. $\mathbf{B} \underline{u}_{jerk, \ell-1}$ is the error introduced to the modeled user position, velocity, and acceleration at epoch ℓ due to user jerk, $\underline{u}_{jerk, \ell-1}$, at epoch $\ell - 1$. $\underline{u}_{jerk, \ell-1}$ has three components given by $[u_{x_{jerk_{\ell-1}}} \quad u_{y_{jerk_{\ell-1}}} \quad u_{z_{jerk_{\ell-1}}}]^T$, which are ECEF x , y , and z components of jerk, respectively. The first nine rows of \mathbf{B} are calculated over the time interval Δt ($= 0.1$ s) as follows.

$$\mathbf{B}(1 : 9, :) = \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\Delta t^3}{6} & \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} & \Delta t \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (10)$$

The last six rows of \mathbf{B} have zero elements corresponding to the GPS and NavIC receiver clock errors. Following Equations 4 and 5, the state error, $\Delta \underline{\mathbf{z}}_{dyn, \ell}^+$, after the measurement update and $\Delta \underline{\mathbf{z}}_{dyn, \ell}^-$ are

$$\Delta \underline{\mathbf{z}}_{dyn, \ell}^+ = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_\ell \mathbf{H}_\ell) \mathbf{F} \Delta \underline{\mathbf{z}}_{dyn, \ell-1}^+ + (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_\ell \mathbf{H}_\ell) \mathbf{B} \underline{\mathbf{u}}_{jerk, \ell-1} \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta \underline{\mathbf{z}}_{dyn, \ell}^- = \mathbf{F} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_\ell \mathbf{H}_\ell) \Delta \underline{\mathbf{z}}_{dyn, \ell-1}^- + \mathbf{B} \underline{\mathbf{u}}_{jerk, \ell-1} \quad (12)$$

The *a priori* dynamic stress error is: $\underline{\epsilon}_{dyn, \ell}^- = \mathbf{H}_\ell \Delta \underline{\mathbf{z}}_{dyn, \ell}^-$. The *a posteriori* dynamic stress error is: $\underline{\epsilon}_{dyn, \ell}^+ = \mathbf{H}_\ell \Delta \underline{\mathbf{z}}_{dyn, \ell}^+$. Since $(\mathbf{H}_\ell, (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_\ell \mathbf{H}_\ell) \mathbf{F})$ is observable, and $((\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_\ell \mathbf{H}_\ell) \mathbf{F}, (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_\ell \mathbf{H}_\ell))$ is stabilizable (see Appendix 6.2 and 6.3), the effect of $\mathbf{B} \underline{\mathbf{u}}_{jerk, \ell-1}$ is reflected in $\underline{\epsilon}_{dyn, \ell}^+$. A similar justification holds for $\underline{\epsilon}_{dyn, \ell}^-$. Using Equation 8 and the dynamic stress error, the total *a priori* 1- σ SS jitters of a VDLL channel i and VFLL channel η before a measurement update are

$$\sigma_{VDLL, \ell}^-(i) = \sigma_{VDLLnoise, \ell}^-(i) + \frac{|\underline{\epsilon}_{dyn, \ell}^-(i)|}{3} \quad (13)$$

$$\sigma_{VFLL, \ell}^-(\eta) = \sigma_{VFLLnoise, \ell}^-(\eta) + \frac{|\underline{\epsilon}_{dyn, \ell}^-(\eta)|}{3} \quad (14)$$

where $|\cdot|$ represents the absolute value. The ‘-’ in the superscript of the preceding equations is replaced with ‘+’ after a measurement update to represent the total *a posteriori* 1- σ SS jitters. It should be noted that these jitters are determined in this paper using theoretical models only. Next, the vector loop jitter is determined from its TF models.

2.2 | Transfer Function Jitter

Traditionally, the jitter is calculated for a scalar tracking loop based on its TF model. Following this approach, the TF jitter is determined for the vector architecture, and used to validate the SS jitter later. As TFs require constant parameters, first, piecewise constant models of vector loops are developed over time intervals, each of duration T_{sub} , without decoupling the VDLL and VFLL. It should be noted that even when there is no dynamic stress error (i.e., for a static user or constant velocity/acceleration user motion), the measurement model matrix, \mathbf{H} , would change with time due to user-satellite relative motion, making the system model time varying. \mathbf{K} may also change due to the adaptive calculation of \mathbf{W} based on C/N_0 . Therefore, piecewise constant models are required for the TF formulations and subsequent jitter calculations. An algorithm to adaptively calculate T_{sub} for a model is given in Appendix (see Section 6.5). Over each interval of T_{sub} duration, \mathbf{H} , \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{K} are assumed to be constant. It should be noted that the minimum value of T_{sub} is 0.1 s, which is the measurement update interval. In this case, a TF model would last only 0.1 s. Following Equations 4 and 5, $\underline{\mathbf{e}}_{\ell+1}^+$ and $\underline{\mathbf{e}}_{\ell+1}^-$ for a given piecewise constant model q of duration T_{sub} reduce to

$$\underline{\mathbf{e}}_{\ell+1}^+ = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_q \mathbf{H}_q) \mathbf{F} \underline{\mathbf{e}}_\ell^+ + (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_q \mathbf{H}_q) \underline{\mathbf{w}}_\ell - \mathbf{K}_q \underline{\boldsymbol{\zeta}}_{\ell+1} \quad (15)$$

$$\underline{\mathbf{e}}_{\ell+1}^- = (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{K}'_q \mathbf{H}_q) \underline{\mathbf{e}}_\ell^- + \underline{\mathbf{w}}_\ell - \mathbf{K}'_q \underline{\boldsymbol{\zeta}}_\ell \quad (16)$$

where \mathbf{K}_q and \mathbf{H}_q are the optimal Kalman gain and actual \mathbf{H} matrices at the beginning of T_{sub} for the model q , respectively. They are kept constant until a new piecewise constant model ($q + 1$) starts. Optimal \mathbf{K} implies the Kalman gain obtained using

the EKF equations with the actual time-varying model of the vector navigation filter. ℓ indicates the indices for the time instants of measurement updates, as before. Since the parameters of the preceding equations are constant, it is possible to find their z-transforms with respect to \underline{w} and $\underline{\zeta}$ as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{e}_q^+(z) &= \underline{e}_{1,q}^+(z) + \underline{e}_{2,q}^+(z) \quad \text{and} \quad \underline{e}_q^-(z) = \underline{e}_{1,q}^-(z) + \underline{e}_{2,q}^-(z) \quad \text{where} \\ \underline{e}_{1,q}^+(z) &= (z\mathbf{I} - (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_q\mathbf{H}_q)\mathbf{F})^{-1}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_q\mathbf{H}_q)\underline{w}(z), \quad \text{and} \quad \underline{e}_{2,q}^+(z) = -(z\mathbf{I} - (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_q\mathbf{H}_q)\mathbf{F})^{-1}\mathbf{K}_q z \underline{\zeta}(z) \\ \underline{e}_{1,q}^-(z) &= (z\mathbf{I} - (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{K}'_q\mathbf{H}_q))^{-1}\underline{w}(z), \quad \text{and} \quad \underline{e}_{2,q}^-(z) = -(z\mathbf{I} - (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{K}'_q\mathbf{H}_q))^{-1}\mathbf{K}'_q \underline{\zeta}(z) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

The preceding two equations provide the z-transforms, $\underline{e}_q^+(z)$ and $\underline{e}_q^-(z)$, of \underline{e}^+ and \underline{e}^- , respectively, for the piecewise constant model q . $\underline{e}_{1,q}(z)$ and $\underline{e}_{2,q}(z)$ represent the z-transform components with respect to \underline{w} and $\underline{\zeta}$, respectively. The z-transforms of $\underline{\epsilon}_e$ and $\underline{\epsilon}_p$ (see after Equation 5 for definition), $\underline{\epsilon}_e(z)$ and $\underline{\epsilon}_p(z)$, are $\mathbf{H}_q \underline{e}_q^+(z)$ and $\mathbf{H}_q \underline{e}_q^-(z)$, respectively. As the z-transform is valid for a finite step size of 0.1 s, it is more appropriate for vector loops than the Laplace transform. The presented formulation does not require the decoupling of VDLL and VFLL, unlike Bhattacharyya, 2018, and also removes other key assumptions of the previous work. The z-domain TFs are used next to find the noise equivalent BWs and jitter.

2.2.1 | Noise Equivalent Bandwidths

The TF matrices relating $\underline{w}(z)$ and $\underline{\zeta}(z)$ to $\underline{\epsilon}_e(z)$ are denoted by $\mathbf{G}_{e1,q}(z)$ and $\mathbf{G}_{e2,q}(z)$, respectively. Similarly, the matrices for $\underline{\epsilon}_p(z)$ are $\mathbf{G}_{p1,q}(z)$ and $\mathbf{G}_{p2,q}(z)$. Using the previous two equations and the paragraph after them, the mathematical expressions of these matrices are summarized next.

$$\mathbf{G}_{e1,q}(z) = \mathbf{H}_q(z\mathbf{I} - (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_q\mathbf{H}_q)\mathbf{F})^{-1}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_q\mathbf{H}_q), \quad \mathbf{G}_{e2,q}(z) = -z\mathbf{H}_q(z\mathbf{I} - (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_q\mathbf{H}_q)\mathbf{F})^{-1}\mathbf{K}_q \quad (18)$$

$$\mathbf{G}_{p1,q}(z) = \mathbf{H}_q(z\mathbf{I} - (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{K}'_q\mathbf{H}_q))^{-1}, \quad \mathbf{G}_{p2,q}(z) = -\mathbf{H}_q(z\mathbf{I} - (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{K}'_q\mathbf{H}_q))^{-1}\mathbf{K}'_q \quad (19)$$

The dimensions of $\mathbf{G}_{e1,q}(z)$ and $\mathbf{G}_{p1,q}(z)$ are $2n \times 15$, and those of $\mathbf{G}_{e2,q}(z)$ and $\mathbf{G}_{p2,q}(z)$ are $2n \times 2n$. Any arbitrary TF matrix, $\mathbf{D}(z)$, of dimension $m \times r$ can be written as

$$\mathbf{D}(z) = \begin{bmatrix} D_{11}(z) & D_{12}(z) & \dots & D_{1r}(z) \\ D_{21}(z) & D_{22}(z) & \dots & D_{2r}(z) \\ & & \vdots & \\ D_{m1}(z) & D_{m2}(z) & \dots & D_{mr}(z) \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

where $D_{i\eta}$ is the TF element in the i th row and η th column. Its one-sided noise equivalent BW is given by

$$\text{BW}^{i\eta} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^\pi D_{i\eta}(e^{j\omega})(D_{i\eta}(e^{j\omega}))^* d\omega \quad (21)$$

where $(D_{i\eta}(e^{j\omega}))^*$ is the complex conjugate transpose of $D_{i\eta}(e^{j\omega})$. $\text{BW}^{i\eta}$ is the BW of a unity gain boxcar filter that will pass the same noise power as that of $D_{i\eta}(e^{j\omega})$. Note that the DC gain is not divided in the preceding equation as different TF elements need not have the same gain (Bhattacharyya, 2018). Thus, $\text{BW}^{i\eta}$ is given by the square of the H_2 norm of $D_{i\eta}(e^{j\omega})$ divided by 2 (i.e., $\text{BW}^{i\eta} = \|D_{i\eta}\|^2/2$). In Matlab, the noise equivalent BWs are calculated for a discrete step size of 0.1 s. Algorithm 1 next calculates the BWs for a generic TF matrix, $\mathbf{D}(z) = \mathbf{P}(z\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}_1)^{-1}\mathbf{B}_1$, of dimension $m \times r$, where \mathbf{P} , \mathbf{A}_1 and \mathbf{B}_1 are some matrices of appropriate dimensions.

Algorithm 1: Noise BW calculation

```

for  $\eta = 1:r$  % column index of the TF matrix,  $\mathbf{D}(z) = \mathbf{P}(z\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}_1)^{-1}\mathbf{B}_1$ 
    % Find the zeros, poles and gains of the TF matrix,  $\mathbf{D}(z)$ , from its state space representation for the  $\eta$ th input
    [zero, pole, gain] = ss2zp( $\mathbf{A}_1$ ,  $\mathbf{B}_1$ ,  $\mathbf{P}$ , zero matrix of dimension  $m \times r$ ,  $\eta$ ); % see Matlab help for details of 'ss2zp'
    for  $i = 1:m$  % row index of the TF matrix,  $\mathbf{D}(z)$ 
        % Find the TF element,  $D_{i\eta}$ , in  $i$ th row and  $\eta$ th column in pole-zero form for a discrete step size of 0.1 s
         $D_{i\eta} = \text{zpk}(\text{zero}(:, i), \text{pole}, \text{gain}(i), 0.1)$ ; % zpk(.) finds the pole-zero form
        % Calculate the noise BW of  $D_{i\eta}$  as  $\text{BW}^{i\eta} = \|D_{i\eta}\|^2/2$ 
         $\text{BW}^{i\eta} = (\text{norm}(D_{i\eta}) \times \text{norm}(D_{i\eta}))/2$ ; % norm(.) calculates the  $H_2$  norm of the TF,  $D_{i\eta}$ 
    end
end
end

```

As there are two input vectors (process noise, \underline{w} and measurement noise, $\underline{\zeta}$), BWs are determined for each of them using the corresponding TF matrix. These BWs are called process noise and measurement noise BWs, respectively. $\text{BW}^{i\eta}$ for $\mathbf{G}_{e_1, q}(z)$, $\mathbf{G}_{e_2, q}(z)$, $\mathbf{G}_{p_1, q}(z)$, and $\mathbf{G}_{p_2, q}(z)$ are denoted by $\text{BW}_{e_1, q}^{i\eta}$, $\text{BW}_{e_2, q}^{i\eta}$, $\text{BW}_{p_1, q}^{i\eta}$ and $\text{BW}_{p_2, q}^{i\eta}$, respectively. Next, the TF noise jitter and dynamic stress error are calculated.

2.2.2 | Noise Jitter and Dynamic Stress Error

Considering both process and measurement noise BWs, the *a posteriori* noise jitters of a VDLL channel i and VFLL channel η for the q th TF model are given as

$$\underline{\sigma}_{VDLL, noise_{tf}}^+(i, q) = \left(2 \sum_{l=1}^{15} \text{BW}_{e_1, q}^{il} \mathbf{Q}(l, l) + 2 \sum_{l=1}^{2n} \text{BW}_{e_2, q}^{il} \mathbf{W}_q(l, l) \right)^{1/2}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (22)$$

$$\underline{\sigma}_{VFLL, noise_{tf}}^+(\eta, q) = \left(2 \sum_{l=1}^{15} \text{BW}_{e_1, q}^{\eta l} \mathbf{Q}(l, l) + 2 \sum_{l=1}^{2n} \text{BW}_{e_2, q}^{\eta l} \mathbf{W}_q(l, l) \right)^{1/2}, \quad \eta = (n+1), \dots, 2n \quad (23)$$

where \mathbf{Q} is of dimension 15×15 . \mathbf{W}_q is the measurement error covariance of the q th TF model obtained adaptively based on C/N_0 when the q th model starts and kept constant until the start of the next model. It is evident that unlike scalar tracking, the noise

jitter of a channel depends on the input noises of all channels. *A priori* noise jitters of the same VDLL and VFLL channels are

$$\underline{\sigma}_{VDLL, noise_{tf}}^-(i, q) = \left(2 \sum_{l=1}^{15} \text{BW}_{p1, q}^{il} \mathbf{Q}(l, l) + 2 \sum_{l=1}^{2n} \text{BW}_{p2, q}^{il} \mathbf{W}_q(l, l) \right)^{1/2}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (24)$$

$$\underline{\sigma}_{VFLL, noise_{tf}}^-(\eta, q) = \left(2 \sum_{l=1}^{15} \text{BW}_{p1, q}^{\eta l} \mathbf{Q}(l, l) + 2 \sum_{l=1}^{2n} \text{BW}_{p2, q}^{\eta l} \mathbf{W}_q(l, l) \right)^{1/2}, \quad \eta = (n+1), \dots, 2n \quad (25)$$

These equations can be derived as follows. If $\mathbf{D}(e^{j\omega})$ is a TF matrix, and \mathbf{R} is a diagonal input noise covariance, then the output noise variance of a channel i is $\mathbf{C}(i, i)$, where \mathbf{C} is

$$\mathbf{C} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \mathbf{D}(e^{i\omega}) \mathbf{R} (\mathbf{D}(e^{j\omega}))^* d\omega \quad (26)$$

The measurement noise covariance, \mathbf{W}_q , is assumed to be a diagonal matrix. It is determined based on C/N_0 and discriminator functions. The process noise covariance, \mathbf{Q} , may have an off-diagonal element due to the receiver clock error, which is given by $2\pi^2 h_{-2} c^2 (\Delta t)^2 / 2$ (Brown & Hwang, 2012) ($\sim 1.77 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^2$, where h_{-2} denotes the h_{-2} parameter of clock noise and is equal to 2×10^{-20} for a low-quality temperature controlled crystal oscillator (TCXO) (Curran et al., 2012a), $\Delta t = 0.1 \text{ s}$, and c is the speed of light). However, its effect is not considered in the TF noise jitter as it is small. The off-diagonal terms of \mathbf{Q} for the user position, velocity and acceleration are considered zero in this paper, thus allowing Equations 22 - 25 to be valid. A diagonal \mathbf{Q} is also reasonable for an update interval of 0.1 s (Groves, 2013). Although non-consideration of the off-diagonal elements of \mathbf{Q} does not compromise performance for the simulation studies of this paper, they will be accounted for in the future work. Figure 2 depicts how input noises, \underline{w} and $\underline{\zeta}$, propagate through the q th TF model and contribute to the *a priori* noise jitter at the output of VFLL channel η . It should be noted that the TF noise jitter provides steady state values. It is not possible to capture any transient effects in this method. The dynamic stress error is determined next. Unlike the noise jitter, this formulation considers transient effects. Transients can arise due to changes in TF models and user motion.

In order to calculate the dynamic stress error, it is assumed that the user jerk profile (i.e., \underline{u}_{jerk}) is known every measurement update interval of 0.1 s, and remains constant over 0.1 s. The state errors due to jerk before and after measurement updates, $\Delta \underline{z}_{dyn, tf}^-$ and $\Delta \underline{z}_{dyn, tf}^+$, are propagated every 0.1 s through the q th TF model of duration T_{sub} using the following equations, respectively.

$$\Delta \underline{z}_{dyn, tf, \ell}^+ = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_q \mathbf{H}_q) \mathbf{F} \Delta \underline{z}_{dyn, tf, \ell-1}^+ + (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_q \mathbf{H}_q) \mathbf{B} \underline{u}_{jerk, \ell-1} \quad (27)$$

$$\Delta \underline{z}_{dyn, tf, \ell}^- = (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{K}'_q \mathbf{H}_q) \Delta \underline{z}_{dyn, tf, \ell-1}^- + \mathbf{B} \underline{u}_{jerk, \ell-1} \quad (28)$$

Considering $\mathbf{B} \underline{u}_{jerk}$ the input vector, the TF matrices for $\Delta \underline{z}_{dyn, tf}^-$ and $\Delta \underline{z}_{dyn, tf}^+$ are $\mathbf{G}_{dyn, q}^-(z) = (z\mathbf{I} - (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{K}'_q \mathbf{H}_q))^{-1}$ and $\mathbf{G}_{dyn, q}^+(z) = (z\mathbf{I} - (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_q \mathbf{H}_q) \mathbf{F})^{-1} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_q \mathbf{H}_q)$, respectively. $\Delta \underline{z}_{dyn, tf, \ell}^-$ is calculated at each time instant ℓ as the sum of the impulse response of $(z\mathbf{I} - (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{K}'_q \mathbf{H}_q))^{-1}$ due to $\Delta \underline{z}_{dyn, tf, \ell-1}^-$ (see the first term on the right hand side of Equation 28), and the step response of $(z\mathbf{I} - (\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{K}'_q \mathbf{H}_q))^{-1}$ over 0.1 s due to $\mathbf{B} \underline{u}_{jerk, \ell-1}$ only. Similarly, $\Delta \underline{z}_{dyn, tf, \ell}^+$ is determined. Then, the corresponding dynamic stress errors, $\underline{\epsilon}_{dyn, tf, \ell}^-$ and $\underline{\epsilon}_{dyn, tf, \ell}^+$, are obtained by multiplying \mathbf{H}_q by $\Delta \underline{z}_{dyn, tf, \ell}^-$ and $\Delta \underline{z}_{dyn, tf, \ell}^+$, respectively.

FIGURE 2 Graphical representation of noise propagation from input to output through the q th TF model for the *a priori* VPLL noise jitter in channel η . The superscripts of $\mathbf{G}_{p1, q}$ and $\mathbf{G}_{p2, q}$ denote the row and column indices. $\mathcal{N}(\cdot, \cdot)$ represents Gaussian noise with the mean and variance shown inside the parentheses

The total *a posteriori* 1- σ TF jitters of a VDLL channel i and VPLL channel η after a measurement update for the q th TF model are

$$\sigma_{VDLL, tf, \ell}^+(i, q) = \sigma_{VDLL, noise_{tf}}^+(i, q) + \frac{|\epsilon_{dyn, tf, \ell}^+(i)|}{3} \quad (29)$$

$$\sigma_{VPLL, tf, \ell}^+(\eta, q) = \sigma_{VPLL, noise_{tf}}^+(\eta, q) + \frac{|\epsilon_{dyn, tf, \ell}^+(\eta)|}{3} \quad (30)$$

Likewise, the *a priori* jitter can be calculated before measurement updates. Vector loop jitter thresholds and a collective metric to represent overall performance are described next. They are used in the simulation studies to theoretically predict the conditions that would lead to loss of lock.

3 | COLLECTIVE JITTER METRIC FOR LOSS OF LOCK DETECTION

In the previous formulations, the *a priori* and *a posteriori* vector loop jitters (both SS and TF) are calculated every 0.1 s, considering thermal noise, and receiver clock and dynamic stress errors. In this section, a loss of lock detection mechanism is designed using the SS jitter described in Section 2.1. Following Ward et al., 2006, the 3- σ jitter threshold for loss of lock detection is $d/2$ for code phase tracking, where d is the Early-Late correlator spacing (= 1 chip in this paper). For carrier frequency tracking, it is $1/(4T)$ for the atan2 discriminator, where T is the coherent integration time. These are proposed as conservative rule-of-thumb thresholds in the reference probably to have a safe margin from the noise-free linear pull-in range of the respective discriminators (Curran et al., 2012b; Curran, 2015). If the jitter exceeds its threshold, it is likely that the noisy discriminator

output will also cross its pull-in range. It is important to note that the prescribed jitter threshold for carrier frequency tracking explicitly depends on T . In the vector loop implementation of this paper, T is 20 ms for the VDLL, and 10 ms for the VFLL as two 10-ms prompt correlator pairs are needed to form the carrier frequency discriminator outputs. Hence, for loss of lock detection, vector loop jitters of all channels are calculated every 20 ms so that they are obtained at the discriminator and code/carrier update rate, which is also the prediction step size of the navigation filter, and the aforementioned threshold can be applied similar to scalar tracking. In addition, the operations of channels are coupled in vector tracking. Thus, a collective metric accounting for the jitters of all channels is required. For this purpose, appropriate jitter bounds are proposed next.

Figure 3 illustrates the concept of jitter lower and upper bounds for a given channel. As shown in the figure, the time interval $\Delta t (= 0.1 \text{ s})$ is divided into five sub-intervals of 20 ms each. The jitter is calculated every 20 ms using a similar approach to determining the SS jitter discussed before. The thick solid horizontal step represents the jitter upper bound for a channel over a 20-ms interval whereas the dashed horizontal one is the lower bound. The predicted jitter is expected to be contained within the two bounds. The algorithm to calculate the jitter bounds every 20 ms over a 0.1-s interval is provided next.

FIGURE 3 Illustration of jitter lower and upper bounds for a channel over 20 ms intervals. For a decreasing trend, the bounds will be interchanged. That is, there are two bounds: One of them corresponds to the beginning of a 20-ms interval, and the other to the end

Algorithm 2: Calculation of jitter bounds every 20 ms

% Calculation of noise jitter every 20 ms between time steps ℓ and $\ell + 1$

% Perform measurement update of the *a priori* state error covariance

$$\Sigma_{\ell}^{+} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_{\ell}\mathbf{H}_{\ell})\Sigma_{\ell}^{-}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_{\ell}\mathbf{H}_{\ell})^T + \mathbf{K}_{\ell}\mathbf{W}_{\ell}\mathbf{K}_{\ell}^T;$$

$\Sigma_{temp,1} = \Sigma_{\ell}^{+}$; % Save Σ_{ℓ}^{+} to a temporary variable for jitter upper bound calculation

$\Sigma_{temp,2} = \Sigma_{\ell}^{+}$; % Save Σ_{ℓ}^{+} to another temporary variable for jitter lower bound calculation

for index = 1:5

```

% Propagation of state error covariance over 20 ms for the upper bound (following the convention of Figure 3)
Sigma_temp, 1 = F' Sigma_temp, 1 (F')^T;
Sigma_temp, 3 = Sigma_temp, 1 + (index)*Q/5; % One-fifth of process noise covariance Q is added every 20 ms
G_temp = H_l Sigma_temp, 3 H_l^T; % Project Sigma_temp, 3 to code phase and Doppler domains
temp = diag(G_temp); % Save the diagonal terms to an array, temp
noise_jitter_ub(:, index) = sqrt(temp); % 1-sigma noise jitter upper bounds of all channels at the end of every 20 ms

% Propagation of state error covariance for the lower bound
Sigma_temp, 3 = Sigma_temp, 2 + (index-1)*Q/5;
Sigma_temp, 2 = F' Sigma_temp, 2 (F')^T; % For next iteration
G_temp = H_l Sigma_temp, 3 H_l^T; % Project Sigma_temp, 3 to code phase and Doppler domains
temp = diag(G_temp); % Save the diagonal terms to an array, temp
noise_jitter_lb(:, index) = sqrt(temp); % 1-sigma noise jitter lower bounds of all channels at the beginning of every 20 ms
end

% Calculation of dynamic stress error every 20 ms

% Calculate Delta z_dyn+, l and Delta z_dyn-, l+1 using Equations 11 and 12, respectively
% Calculate a posteriori and a priori dynamic stress errors at l and l + 1, respectively
epsilon_dyn+, l = H_l Delta z_dyn+, l % A posteriori dynamic stress error
epsilon_dyn-, l+1 = H_l Delta z_dyn-, l+1 % A priori dynamic stress error; H does not change much over 0.1 s
% Assuming a linear variation of the error over 0.1 s, a slope is calculated. Note that the absolute value
% is taken
slope = (|epsilon_dyn-, l+1|/3 - |epsilon_dyn+, l|/3) / 0.1;
% Calculate the 1-sigma total jitters of both VDLL and VFLL channels at the beginning and end of every 20 ms
for index = 1:5
    % 1-sigma upper bounds
    % Note that the last iteration gives a jitter identical with the total a priori jitter after 0.1 s (i.e., Equations 13 and 14)
    jitter_ub(:, index) = noise_jitter_ub(:, index) + (|epsilon_dyn+, l|/3 + slope*0.02*index);
    % 1-sigma lower bounds (Note that the first iteration gives the total a posteriori 1-sigma jitter at l)
    jitter_lb(:, index) = noise_jitter_lb(:, index) + (|epsilon_dyn+, l|/3 + slope*0.02*(index-1));
end

Sigma_l+1^- = Sigma_temp, 1 + Q % a priori state error covariance for time step (l + 1)

```

The final jitter upper bound of a channel every 0.1 s is the average of five jitter upper bounds each corresponding to the end of 20 ms, following the convention of Figure 3. Similarly, the final lower bound is the average of five lower bounds each at the beginning

of 20 ms. The reason behind averaging the bounds is that if the majority of the five upper bounds over 0.1 s cross the threshold, their average would as well. The mean of the averaged bounds across all VFLL channels and across all VDLL channels is also determined. First, it is separately calculated over all GPS channels and all NavIC channels, and then the two means are averaged. The averaged one is called the mean jitter upper or lower bound for the VFLL (or VDLL). The mean bound is considered a collective jitter metric, reflecting overall vector loop performance, and compared against the jitter threshold mentioned earlier for loss of lock detection every 0.1 s. The effectiveness of the mean jitter upper bound for detecting loss of lock will be shown in the Simulation Studies. It should be noted that for a decreasing jitter over 0.1 s (i.e., the reverse trend of Figure 3), the bound at the beginning of 20 ms becomes the upper bound. Since it would not be known if the jitter increases or decreases over a 0.1 s interval, both bounds at the beginning and end of 20 ms are calculated. The overall sequence of operations for the calculation of SS and TF jitters and jitter metric is described in Appendix 6.6. In this paper, they are calculated offline. Simulation results are presented next.

4 | SIMULATION STUDIES

GPS L1 and NavIC L5 signals are simulated for a high dynamic unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) trajectory using Accord's GNSS simulator (Accord Software and Systems, 2024). The generated signals are recorded by an IFEN intermediate frequency (IF) data recorder with a 20 MHz sampling frequency. The recorded IF data is post-processed by a software vector receiver with models discussed in the beginning of Section 2. The simulator introduces the Ionospheric and Tropospheric delays using the Klobuchar and RTCA98 models, respectively. The receiver removes these errors using the Klobuchar and Hopfield models. The UAV trajectory, skyplot and variations of jerk magnitudes are depicted in Figure 4. Jerk can be as high as 16 g/s, which lasts about 20 s at two separate instants during the maneuver. Different other jerk magnitudes are also labeled in the figure. While the signals are simulated at 42-44 dB-Hz, artificial white noise is injected into the recorded IF data to create low C/N_0 environments. Thus, low C/N_0 along with high dynamics creates scenarios ideal for vector loop jitter analysis.

The measurement noise covariance, \mathbf{W} , is adaptively determined based on C/N_0 . Two sets of process noise covariance denoted by \mathbf{Q}_1 and \mathbf{Q}_2 are considered in this paper for loss of lock analysis with different jerks. For the user position, velocity and acceleration states along the ECEF x-, y-, and z-axes, they are $\text{diag}([0.5 \ 0.2 \ 8 \ 0.5 \ 0.2 \ 8 \ 0.7 \ 0.2 \ 8])$ (used for all C/N_0 s), and $\text{diag}([0.5 \ 0.2 \ 0.1 \ 0.5 \ 0.2 \ 0.5 \ 0.7 \ 0.2 \ 0.2])$ (used only for C/N_0 s of 30 dB-Hz or lower), respectively, where $\text{diag}()$ is a diagonal matrix. The first three elements are for the x components of the user position, velocity and acceleration in m^2 , $(\text{m/s})^2$ and $(\text{m/s}^2)^2$, respectively; the next three are for the y components; and the last three are for the z components. Once set, they are not changed with C/N_0 or dynamics. For \mathbf{Q}_1 , the clock bias and drift states are calculated using the h_0 and h_{-2} parameters of a TCXO (Brown & Hwang, 2012). The portion of the \mathbf{Q}_1 matrix for the receiver clock bias (in m^2), drift (in $(\text{m/s})^2$) and drift rate (in $(\text{m/s}^2)^2$) (same for both GPS and NavIC) is: $\mathbf{Q}_{clk} = \begin{bmatrix} q_\varphi \Delta t + q_\omega (\Delta t)^3 / 3 & q_\omega (\Delta t)^2 / 2 & 0 \\ q_\omega (\Delta t)^2 / 2 & q_\omega (\Delta t) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$, where $q_\varphi = \frac{h_0}{2} c^2$ and $q_\omega = 2\pi^2 h_{-2} c^2$; the numerical values of the h_0 and h_{-2} clock parameters are 1×10^{-21} and 2×10^{-20} , respectively; and c is the speed of light. For \mathbf{Q}_2 , at mean C/N_0 (i.e., the average of all channel values) of 30 dB-Hz, \mathbf{Q}_{clk} is taken as $\text{diag}([3 \ 2.5 \ 1])$ to adequately deal with dynamics. It is not changed until 21 dB-Hz. For mean C/N_0 at or below 20 dB-Hz, \mathbf{Q}_{clk} of \mathbf{Q}_2 is considered $\text{diag}([3 \ 1.5 \ 1])$ to stabilize the filter

FIGURE 4 Simulated user trajectory, skyplot and user jerk magnitude. ‘G’ denotes GPS and ‘N’ denotes NavIC satellites in the skyplot. Circle indicates the end of a satellite trace

even without high dynamics. Larger Q_{clk} is chosen for Q_2 than that for Q_1 to compensate for small acceleration terms that are not adequate during high dynamics. It should be noted that Q_1 (except the clock bias and drift terms of Q_{clk}) and Q_2 are chosen by trial and error to make the vector loops work. Both sets of Q ensure that the filter learns from its measurements and that the errors in the estimated position, velocity and acceleration terms are bounded by the respective $3\text{-}\sigma$ bounds in the absence of user jerk for the ranges of C/N_0 considered in this paper. For Q_1 , the acceleration terms are kept high to account for the propagation model inaccuracies during high dynamics with jerk, and position and velocity terms have small, nominal values. For Q_2 , the acceleration terms are kept small, and clock terms are chosen so that loss of lock can be demonstrated at different jerks. While Q_1 will be shown to better handle dynamics than Q_2 , the latter effectively illustrates that jitter can detect loss of lock at different jerks with the help of the same UAV simulation. It will also be shown how with two different Q matrices, the total jitter changes, and for both cases the detection of loss of lock would be validated by the divergence of the estimated states in the simulation.

Before loss of lock analysis, however, it is important to compare the SS and TF jitters, and to show that jitter can predict the steady state errors in the code and carrier channels in the presence of noise alone. To this end, first, the SS jitter is validated with the TF jitter after initial transients of the filter have died down with Q_1 process noise covariance. The validation results of both the total *a priori* and *a posteriori* SS and TF jitters are shown in Table 1, where the mean $\pm 3\text{-}\sigma$ values of the two jitter difference across all VDLL and VFLL channels and time steps are reported for different ranges of C/N_0 . It should be noted that C/N_0 s are lowered from the default range of (42-44) dB-Hz at 126.1 s into the run and then restored at 1026.1 s. The scenario is run multiple times, each time with one set of C/N_0 s noted in the table. The difference between the SS and TF jitters of a channel is expressed as a

Range of C/N_0 (dB-Hz)	Mean $\pm 3\text{-}\sigma$ value of the difference between the total <i>a posteriori</i> SS and TF jitters (%)	Mean $\pm 3\text{-}\sigma$ value of the difference between the total <i>a priori</i> SS and TF jitters (%)
42-44	0.02484 ± 0.7139	0.0139 ± 1.0486
38.6 - 40	0.0177 ± 1.2878	0.01095 ± 1.69
33.5 - 35	0.0511 ± 3.761	0.03657 ± 4.456
28.5 - 31	0.0732 ± 4.71	0.0568 ± 5.203

TABLE 1

Mean $\pm 3\text{-}\sigma$ value of the difference between the SS and TF jitters is calculated over all channels and time steps. The difference is expressed as a percentage of the corresponding TF jitter.

percentage of its TF jitter before calculating the mean and standard deviation. For a fair comparison, it is ensured that both SS and TF jitters use the same piecewise constant models (see the beginning of Section 2.2), and then they are calculated theoretically but using the \mathbf{K} , \mathbf{H} and \mathbf{W} matrices obtained from the vector loop runs corresponding to each model. The jitter difference is calculated every T_{sub} s (i.e. at the end of a constant model) so that the transient effects due to model change captured by the SS jitter are reduced. The results in the table indicate that both SS noise jitter and dynamic stress error are in good agreement with their TF counterparts, thus establishing an equivalence between two differently calculated jitters and validating the use of the SS jitter. The higher differences at lower C/N_0 s can be attributed to the following reasons: 1. The transition from high C/N_0 to relatively low C/N_0 at 126.1 s and vice versa at 1026.1 s results in transients, which take some time to die down. The TF noise jitter captures steady state values, but the SS noise jitter reflects transients. 2. T_{sub} values are mostly 0.1 s at low C/N_0 s, meaning the TF models are changed just after 0.1 s. While changes can cause minor transients, these effects would not be evident in the TF noise jitter.

Having established an equivalence between the SS and TF jitters, steady state jitter performance is analyzed at different noise levels in the absence of the dynamic stress error with 16 visible satellites. For this purpose, the duration of data between 330 s and 450 s into the run is considered when the UAV moves with a small constant acceleration (i.e., no jerk), and the filter has reached steady state. More precisely, it is studied if the jitter is able to predict the code phase and Doppler error variations. The selected duration is a reasonably long one after lowering C/N_0 when steady state performance can be analyzed at different noise levels.

For a stringent comparison, the code phase and Doppler errors of a channel at a time of reception, t_r , are determined differently from that defined after Equation 5, which forms the basis for the jitter calculation. If ρ_{tr} is the true pseudorange of a channel at t_r and ρ_{pr} is what the vector receiver predicts, then they are given by

$$\rho_{tr} = c(t_r - t_t^{\text{true}}) \quad (31)$$

$$\rho_{pr} = c(t_r - t_t^{\text{pred}}) \quad (32)$$

where t_t^{true} is the true time of transmission, and t_t^{pred} is its receiver-predicted value. The difference between the two pseudoranges is

$$\rho_{tr} - \rho_{pr} = c(t_t^{\text{pred}} - t_t^{\text{true}}) \quad (33)$$

Since the transmitted code of a GNSS satellite gives a fine measure of the signal transmission time, the code phase alignment error of the receiver results in an error in the calculation of the time. Thus, the *a priori* code phase error of the vector receiver in m would be $(\rho_{tr} - \rho_{pr})$. This error is expected to be bounded by the total *a priori* $3\text{-}\sigma$ code phase jitter, whose $1\text{-}\sigma$ value is given by Equation 13 after conversion to m. It should be noted that the dynamic stress error component can be neglected in the absence of jerk. Similarly, the *a priori* version of Equation 29 should be considered for the TF jitter. The *a priori* carrier Doppler error of a channel is given as the difference between the true Doppler and receiver-predicted Doppler, which should be bounded by the $3\text{-}\sigma$ value of the total jitter given by Equation 14. Likewise, the *a priori* TF jitter can be calculated following Section 2.2.

For a satellite, the true pseudorange measurement and its rate (needed for the Doppler calculation) are obtained from the simulator log files every 0.1 s, considering all error sources except the receiver clock bias and drift. As the clock terms are not known, their estimates by the vector receiver at high C/N_0 of (42-44) dB-Hz are assumed to be truth, and added to the measurements derived from the simulator files at appropriate times after extrapolation. The code phase and carrier Doppler errors of select GPS and NavIC satellites calculated as explained before alongside the total *a priori* SS and TF jitters are depicted in Figures 5 and 6 at mean C/N_0 of 30 dB-Hz. Both figures have the \mathbf{Q}_1 process noise covariance. The code phase and carrier frequency discriminator outputs, which are the receiver's noisy estimates of the code and carrier errors, are also illustrated along with their respective $\pm 3\text{-}\sigma$ bounds. As the discriminator outputs are the innovation vector of the navigation filter, their bounds are determined from the diagonal elements of the innovation covariance matrix. Panel (c) of the two figures shows the SS jitter whereas panel (d) is for the TF jitter.

FIGURE 5 Steady state code phase jitter performance in two channels at mean C/N_0 of 30 dB-Hz. Code phase discriminator outputs (O/P) along with $\pm 3\text{-}\sigma$ bounds are also shown. Panel (c) depicts the SS jitter, and (d) the TF jitter, as obtained from their respective vector loop runs

FIGURE 6 Steady state carrier Doppler jitter performance in two channels at mean C/N_0 of 30 dB-Hz. Carrier frequency discriminator outputs along with $\pm 3\text{-}\sigma$ innovation bounds are also shown. Panel (c) depicts the SS jitter, and (d) illustrates the TF jitter, as obtained from their respective vector loop runs

FIGURE 7 Comparison of $\pm 3\text{-}\sigma$ jitter metric (or mean jitter upper bound) against code phase and carrier Doppler errors at 30 dB-Hz between 330 and 450 s into the run with Q_1 process noise covariance

FIGURE 8 Comparison of $\pm 3\text{-}\sigma$ VFLJ jitter metric (or mean VFLJ jitter upper bound) against carrier Doppler errors at 23 dB-Hz between 330 and 450 s into the run

For the results in panels (b) and (d), piecewise constant models discussed in the beginning of Section 2.2 are used because they are needed for the calculation of the TF jitter. For panels (a) and (c), the original, time-varying vector loop implementation is used as the calculation of the SS jitter does not need piecewise constant models. Both figures show that the total *a priori* SS and TF jitters bound the corresponding code phase and carrier Doppler errors in their respective vector loop runs. Although not shown, other channels offer similar performance.

The metric (i.e., the mean jitter upper bound of the VDLL/VFLJ) proposed in Section 3 is expected to capture the vector loop behavior on average over an interval of 0.1 s. Therefore, it is imperative to study if it is able to predict the code and carrier channel errors. For this purpose, Figure 7(a) plots the maximum and minimum code phase errors among all channels before and after the measurement updates (i.e., the maximum and minimum of the *a priori* and *a posteriori* errors over a 0.1-s interval) at 30 dB-Hz, and the corresponding $\pm 3\text{-}\sigma$ VDLL jitter metric. Panel (b) of the same figure illustrates this for the carrier channels. It is evident that the jitter metric is a good indicator of the code and carrier channel performance. Finally, the carrier channel behavior is studied at mean C/N_0 of 23.1 dB-Hz in Figure 8 for both Q_1 and Q_2 process noise covariances. While the carrier Doppler error exceeds the jitter metric in panel (a) sometimes, the overall performance is acceptable. The code phase error plots, although omitted for brevity, are mostly bounded by their respective $3\text{-}\sigma$ jitter metrics. It is important to note that the $3\text{-}\sigma$ jitter metric represents the collective performance of all vector loop channels on average, and hence, there could be sporadic level crossings at some instants.

The previous analysis indicates that jitter can predict the code and carrier channel errors in the presence of noise. Next, loss of lock performance of the jitter is studied with jerk. For this purpose, the proposed metric with the SS jitter in Section 3 is shown in

Figure 9 for the VFLL at different C/N_0 s. Artificial white noise is injected into the recorded IF data from 126.1 s into the run in panels (a) and (c) and from 76.1 s in (b) and (d) to lower C/N_0 s from the default range of (42-44) dB-Hz. This results in an abrupt increase in the jitter before 200 s in the figure. C/N_0 s are restored after 1000 s. The mean value of the reduced C/N_0 s over all channels and time steps before loss of lock is indicated on top of each panel. It should be noted that each panel shows results for a different run executed independently of the others. The solid dark line in the figure represents the $1\text{-}\sigma$ jitter threshold, $1/(12T)$, for loss of lock detection. It is 8.33 Hz for T equal to 10 ms. ‘State Divergence Onset’ indicates the instant when one of the vector loop states during the simulation starts to oscillate/diverge, meaning its error just crosses the $3\text{-}\sigma$ bound of the filter. This is eventually followed by error growth in all states. The marker in the figure, on the other hand, indicates the instant when the jitter metric crosses its threshold by a sufficient margin. Figure 9(a) and (b) show the results with Q_1 process noise covariance whereas (c) and (d) are for Q_2 . In (c) the mean jitter upper bound crosses its threshold just before the onset of the actual state error growth. In (b) and (d) the threshold is crossed 5.2 s and 3 s after the onset, respectively. On the other hand, panel (a) with Q_1 process noise covariance

FIGURE 9 Mean VFLL jitter upper bound at different mean C/N_0 s. Initial epochs with transients are not considered. Although not shown in the figure, the mean jitter lower bound (i.e., the mean of bounds calculated at the beginning of 20 ms intervals in Figure 3) exceeds the threshold first time at 789.3 s, 781.5 s and 594.3 s in (b), (c) and (d), respectively. The abrupt change in jitter before 200 s and after 1000 s is due to decrease in C/N_0 from (42-44) dB-Hz and increase afterward

does not have any loss of lock as the vector loops work for the entire duration in this case. Thus, Figure 9 illustrates that the proposed jitter metric holds promise to represent collective vector loop performance, and could be a good indicator of loss of lock. Although the jitter lower bound is not shown, the time instants when the mean bound crosses the threshold are provided in the figure caption. Comparing with Figure 4(d), it can be stated that loss of lock occurs during 16.71 g/s in panels (b) and (c) of the figure, and during 9.954 g/s in panel (d). It is evident that vector loops offer better dynamic performance with \mathbf{Q}_1 than that with \mathbf{Q}_2 . However, the choice of \mathbf{Q}_2 allows for the demonstration of loss of lock at two different jerk levels. It is also important to note that the x-axis limits are less than 1000 s in panels (b) and (d) as the jitter is plotted until the vector loop algorithm has a minimum number of satellites for positioning. Jitter calculation after loss of lock when the position and velocity errors are sufficiently large is also not valid because the linearized model of the vector loops does not hold. Therefore, plotting the jitter after a few hundred seconds of continuous loss of lock does not carry any meaningful information. This is evident in panel (c) of the figure. In this case, after indicating loss of lock for 244.7 s, the jitter metric drops below the threshold when C/N_0 s are restored to (42-44) dB-Hz, although the reduced value is more than what it was earlier for the same C/N_0 s. A careful inspection also reveals that after restoring C/N_0 s, the individual channel jitters exhibit large variations with time in comparison with a smooth profile earlier. The actual vector loop simulation, on the other hand, has diverged significantly in 244.7 s, and in the remaining few seconds the EKF navigation filter does not show any tendency to recover from the divergence.

5 | CONCLUSION

In this paper, the SS jitter and TF jitter of the non-coherent vector architecture are presented for a theoretical evaluation of the tracking loop performance. In this context, z-domain TF models of the time varying vector architecture are developed without decoupling the VDLL and VFLL. Noise equivalent BWs are also calculated. It is shown that the SS and TF jitters are in close agreement, which proves their equivalence. Appropriate jitter bounds are proposed for measurement update intervals higher than 20 ms so that existing loss of lock thresholds can be applied. A metric to represent the collective performance of all channels is identified for loss of lock detection. Steady state jitter performance in the absence of dynamic stress error is analyzed in detail. Then, high dynamic simulations of GPS L1 and NavIC L5 signals are used to showcase that the proposed metric holds promise for detecting loss of lock at different jerk levels. In the future work, extensive simulations with different user trajectories will be performed to assess the jitter performance. The feasibility of using the user jerk calculated from the estimated user acceleration will be studied to find the total jitter in real time. The off-diagonal elements of the process noise covariance matrix will be accounted for in the TF jitter calculation. A better metric to represent collective performance may also be identified. Adaptive determination of the process noise covariance matrix may also be implemented (Chen et al., 2024). Jitter is theoretically determined in this paper. A suitable methodology to estimate it will be developed in the future work.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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6 | APPENDIX

In this section, first, the measurement model matrix of the vector navigation filter is defined. Then, the observability and reachability properties of some matrices are proved. Finally, the algorithms for T_{sub} and vector jitter calculations are described.

6.1 | Measurement Model Matrix of Vector Navigation Filter

The measurement model matrix of the vector navigation filter at time t_ℓ is $\mathbf{H}_\ell = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H}_{x,\ell} & \mathbf{H}_{y,\ell} & \mathbf{H}_{z,\ell} & \mathbf{H}_{clk,\ell}^G & \mathbf{H}_{clk,\ell}^N \end{bmatrix}$. Its components are

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{H}_{\xi, \ell} &= \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{u}_{1, \ell}^{\xi} \frac{f_{code}}{c} & \dots & \tilde{u}_{n_G+1, \ell}^{\xi} \frac{f_{code}}{c} & \dots & \tilde{u}_{n, \ell}^{\xi} \frac{f_{code}}{c} & [\mathbf{0}]_{1 \times n} \\ & [\mathbf{0}]_{1 \times n} & & \tilde{u}_{1, \ell}^{\xi} \frac{f_{carr}^G}{c} & \dots & \tilde{u}_{n, \ell}^{\xi} \frac{f_{carr}^N}{c} \\ & & [\mathbf{0}]_{1 \times 2n} & & & \end{bmatrix}^T, \quad \xi = x, y, z \\
\mathbf{H}_{clk, \ell}^G &= \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{f_{code}}{c} & \dots & -\frac{f_{code}}{c} & [\mathbf{0}]_{1 \times n_N} & [\mathbf{0}]_{1 \times n} \\ [\mathbf{0}]_{1 \times n} & & -\frac{f_{carr}^G}{c} & \dots & -\frac{f_{carr}^G}{c} & [\mathbf{0}]_{1 \times n_N} \\ & & [\mathbf{0}]_{1 \times 2n} & & & \end{bmatrix}^T, \\
\mathbf{H}_{clk, \ell}^N &= \begin{bmatrix} [\mathbf{0}]_{1 \times n_G} & -\frac{f_{code}}{c} & \dots & -\frac{f_{code}}{c} & [\mathbf{0}]_{1 \times n} \\ [\mathbf{0}]_{1 \times n_G} & [\mathbf{0}]_{1 \times n} & & -\frac{f_{carr}^N}{c} & \dots & -\frac{f_{carr}^N}{c} \\ & [\mathbf{0}]_{1 \times 2n} & & & & \end{bmatrix}^T
\end{aligned}$$

where $[\mathbf{0}]$ denotes a matrix or vector of zero elements. $\tilde{u}_{i, \ell}^{\xi} = x, y$ or z component of the line of sight vector in ECEF at t_{ℓ} for the i^{th} satellite, with $\xi = x, y, z$. n_G is the number of visible GPS satellites. n_N is the number of visible NavIC satellites at t_{ℓ} (i.e. $n_G + n_N = n$). The first to third columns of $\mathbf{H}_{clk, \ell}^G$ and $\mathbf{H}_{clk, \ell}^N$ correspond to the receiver clock bias, drift and drift rate for GPS and NavIC, respectively. f_{code} denotes the transmitted C/A-code chipping rate, which is the same for both constellations. f_{carr}^G and f_{carr}^N are GPS and NavIC carrier frequencies, respectively. c is the speed of light.

Next, the observability and reachability properties of some matrices are proved. It should be noted that the subscript ℓ denoting the time instants in the matrices is dropped for ease of representation.

6.2 | Proof that $(\mathbf{H}, (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F})$ is Observable

First, it is proved that $(\mathbf{H}, \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH}))$ is observable. It has been assumed that (\mathbf{H}, \mathbf{F}) of the vector navigation filter is observable. Therefore, $(\mathbf{F}^T, \mathbf{H}^T)$ is reachable. Using the reachability property (i.e., the PBH eigenvector tests (Kailath, 1980)), it can be stated that, for any left eigenvector, \underline{v}^T , of \mathbf{F}^T for the eigenvalue, λ , $\underline{v}^T \mathbf{F}^T = \lambda \underline{v}^T$ and $\underline{v}^T \mathbf{H}^T \neq 0$. Let \underline{u}^T be a left eigenvector of $(\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH}))^T$ such that $\underline{u}^T \mathbf{H}^T = 0$. If the corresponding eigenvalue of $(\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH}))^T$ is γ , then using $\underline{u}^T \mathbf{H}^T = 0$, one can write

$$\underline{u}^T (\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH}))^T = \underline{u}^T \mathbf{F}^T = \gamma \underline{u}^T \quad (34)$$

This implies that \underline{u}^T is a left eigenvector of $(\mathbf{F})^T$ and $\underline{u}^T \mathbf{H}^T = 0$, which contradicts the reachability criterion of $(\mathbf{F}^T, \mathbf{H}^T)$ stated before. Thus, for a left eigenvector, \underline{u}^T , of $(\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH}))^T$, $\underline{u}^T \mathbf{H}^T \neq 0$. That is, $((\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH}))^T, \mathbf{H}^T)$ is reachable or $(\mathbf{H}, \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH}))$ is observable.

Next, it is shown that $(\mathbf{H}, (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F})$ is observable (or, $((\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F})^T, \mathbf{H}^T)$ is reachable). Let $\underline{\omega}^T$ be a left eigenvector of $((\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F})^T$ for the eigenvalue, α . Then,

$$\underline{\omega}^T ((\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F})^T = \alpha \underline{\omega}^T \quad (35)$$

Post-multiplying \mathbf{F}^T on either side of the preceding equation, and writing $\underline{\omega}^T \mathbf{F}^T$ as $\underline{\omega}_1^T$, $\underline{\omega}_1^T (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})^T \mathbf{F}^T = \alpha \underline{\omega}_1^T$. Thus, $\underline{\omega}_1^T$ is a left eigenvector of $(\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH}))^T$. Since $((\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH}))^T, \mathbf{H}^T)$ has been proved to be reachable, $\underline{\omega}_1^T \mathbf{H}^T \neq 0$. So, $\mathbf{H} \underline{\omega}_1 \neq 0$.

Next, it is shown that $\mathbf{H}\underline{\omega} \neq 0$. Since $\underline{\omega}^T$ is a left eigenvector of $((\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F})^T$, proving $\mathbf{H}\underline{\omega} \neq 0$ (or, $\underline{\omega}^T \mathbf{H}^T \neq 0$) would imply that $((\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F})^T, \mathbf{H}^T$ is reachable or $(\mathbf{H}, (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F})$ is observable.

From the expression of \mathbf{F} after Equation 3, it is evident that \mathbf{F} is invertible. Therefore, $\mathbf{H}\underline{\omega} = \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{F})^{-1}\underline{\omega}_1$. As $\mathbf{H}\underline{\omega}_1 \neq 0$, $\underline{\omega}_1 \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathbf{H}^T}$ (the range space of \mathbf{H}^T), which is orthogonal to the null space of \mathbf{H} , $\mathcal{N}_{\mathbf{H}}$. Using the mathematical expression of \mathbf{F} , it can be shown that $\underline{\omega}_1^T (\mathbf{F})^{-1}\underline{\omega}_1$ cannot be zero for a non-zero $\underline{\omega}_1$, meaning \mathbf{F}^{-1} will not project $\underline{\omega}_1$ from $\mathcal{R}_{\mathbf{H}^T}$ to $\mathcal{N}_{\mathbf{H}}$. Therefore, $\mathbf{H}\underline{\omega} \neq 0$, and $(\mathbf{H}, (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F})$ is observable.

6.3 | Proof that $((\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}, (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH}))$ is Stabilizable

As (\mathbf{H}, \mathbf{F}) of the vector navigation filter is observable, there exists a \mathbf{K}' such that the eigenvalues of $(\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{K}'\mathbf{H})$ are less than one (Anderson & Moore, 2005). Alternatively, it can be stated that by suitably selecting \mathbf{K}' , one can arbitrarily place the eigenvalues of $(\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{K}'\mathbf{H})$. Since by definition, \mathbf{F} is invertible, for each \mathbf{K}' , there exists a unique \mathbf{K} such that $\mathbf{K} = (\mathbf{F})^{-1}\mathbf{K}'$. Therefore, for any \mathbf{K}' , $(\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{K}'\mathbf{H})$ is identical with $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})$, where $\mathbf{K} = (\mathbf{F})^{-1}\mathbf{K}'$. It can be easily shown that the eigenvalues of $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}$ are identical with those of $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})$. So the eigenvalues of $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})$ or $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}$ can be arbitrarily placed by selecting a suitable \mathbf{K} .

Let \underline{v}^T be a left eigenvector of $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}$ such that $\underline{v}^T(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH}) = 0$. Hence, $\underline{v}^T(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F} = 0$, which implies that the corresponding eigenvalue of $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}$ is zero. Therefore, $\underline{v}^T(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH}) \neq 0$ for any left eigenvector, \underline{v}^T , of $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}$ for a non-zero eigenvalue. So, if \mathbf{K} is selected such that the eigenvalues of $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}$ are non-zero, $((\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}, (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH}))$ is reachable. If $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}$ has a zero eigenvalue, then $((\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}, (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH}))$ is stabilizable, meaning any uncontrollable modes of $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}$ are stable. This is because the eigenvalues of $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}$ can be arbitrarily placed or made less than one by selecting a suitable \mathbf{K} (see the preceding paragraph). This is true for a stable, working vector navigation filter. Although stabilizability is not required for the calculation of vector loop jitter, the proof in this section indicates that \underline{e}^+ is affected by the process noise input in Equation 4 as all eigenvalues of $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}$ cannot be zero, and hence, some modes of \underline{e}^+ would be controllable or affected by the process noise.

6.4 | Proof that $((\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}, \mathbf{K})$ is Reachable

Let \underline{v}^T be a left eigenvector of $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}$ for the eigenvalue γ such that $\underline{v}^T \mathbf{K} = 0$. Hence, $\underline{v}^T \mathbf{F} = \gamma \underline{v}^T$, which implies that γ is also an eigenvalue of \mathbf{F} . Following the first paragraph of Section 6.3, the eigenvalues of $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}$ can be arbitrarily placed by selecting a suitable \mathbf{K} . For an asymptotically stable navigation filter (i.e., when vector loops are operational with a good number of satellites being tracked), \mathbf{K} should be such that the eigenvalues of $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}$ are less than one. But the eigenvalues of \mathbf{F} are fixed and equal to one. Therefore, $\underline{v}^T \mathbf{K} \neq 0$ for any left eigenvector, \underline{v}^T , of $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}$. So, $((\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{KH})\mathbf{F}, \mathbf{K})$ is reachable.

6.5 | Algorithm for T_{sub} Calculation

The algorithm to calculate T_{sub} , over which \mathbf{H} , \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{K} matrices are assumed to be constant, is given in this section. A new model is started (i.e., the duration of T_{sub} for the existing TF model is determined), if one of the following happens: 1. satellite

visibility changes; 2. The 2-norm of the difference between the actual time-varying \mathbf{H} matrix and that of the existing model exceeds a certain threshold; 3. The 2-norm of the difference between the optimal \mathbf{K} (i.e., the \mathbf{K} obtained using the EKF equations with the actual time-varying model of the filter) and that of the existing piecewise constant model exceeds a certain threshold. In order to find this, the optimal \mathbf{K} is computed at every measurement update interval. The algorithm for T_{sub} calculation is described next.

Algorithm 3: T_{sub} calculation

```

if(first measurement update)
    tf_counter = 1; % TF model counter is one at the beginning
end
vis_flag = 0; % Set visibility flag to zero at each epoch. If satellite visibility
% changes (i.e., a new satellite comes or a satellite sets/is blocked), a new model
% should be started. To indicate that, vis_flag is later set to one, when needed.
% Set the maximum 2-norm of the difference between the actual  $\mathbf{H}$  and that of the existing TF model
delta_H_th = 0.01;
% Set the maximum 2-norm of the difference between the optimal  $\mathbf{K}$  matrix and that of the existing TF
% model (delta_K_th) based on  $C/N_0$ . The values of delta_K_th are selected by trial and error. It should be noted that
% lower values are also allowed as minimum  $T_{sub}$  is fixed to 0.1 s. Higher  $T_{sub}$  results in a TF model being
% valid for a longer duration, but performance should not degrade due to longer  $T_{sub}$ .
if(average  $C/N_0$  over all channels > 30)
    delta_K_th = 0.5;
else if(average  $C/N_0$  > 20)
    delta_K_th = 0.1;
else
    delta_K_th = 0.001;
end
if(a new satellite has come, or one or more satellites have set/are blocked)
    vis_flag = 1; % As change in visibility may create transients, a new model should be started
end
if(vis_flag == 1 || number of measurement updates == 20) % First 19 0.1 s intervals are skipped to avoid large transients
     $T_{sub}(tf\_counter) = 0.1$ ; % Start a new model
    % Make  $\mathbf{K}$ ,  $\mathbf{H}$  and  $\mathbf{W}$  of this model equal to optimal  $\mathbf{K}$ , and actual  $\mathbf{H}$  and  $\mathbf{W}$  at the current time, respectively
    tf_counter = tf_counter + 1; % Increment the model counter to point to the next model
else if(number of measurement updates > 20)
    delta_K = Optimal  $\mathbf{K}$  - constant  $\mathbf{K}$  of existing model; % Find delta_K

```

```

delta_H = actual H - constant H of existing model; % Find delta_H
if(norm(delta_K) < delta_K_th and norm(delta_H) < delta_H_th)
     $T_{sub}(tf\_counter-1) = T_{sub}(tf\_counter-1) + 0.1$ ; % Increment the duration of the
    % existing model, and retain previous K, H and W
else
     $T_{sub}(tf\_counter) = 0.1$ ; % Start a new model
    % Make K, H and W of this model equal to optimal K, and actual H and W at the current time, respectively
    tf_counter = tf_counter + 1; % Increment the model counter to point to the next model
end
end
end

```

6.6 | Algorithm for Overall Sequence of Operations for Jitter Calculation

Algorithm 4: Overall sequence of operations for the calculation of SS and TF jitters and jitter metric

```

% Get all H, W and K matrices and  $T_{sub}$  values from the vector loop run
tf_index = 1; % TF model index initialized to one
loop_count = 0.1; % Iteration counter of step size 0.1
for t = 0:0.1:total duration % Time loop iteration every 0.1 s
    % Calculation of the total a priori and a posteriori SS jitters, and jitter metric for loss of lock detection
    % Execute Algorithm 2 to calculate the five jitter lower and upper bounds over a 0.1-s interval between any two time
    steps  $\ell$  and  $(\ell + 1)$ . Note that the first of five lower bounds is the total a posteriori SS jitter at  $\ell$ , and the last of five upper
    bounds is the total a priori SS jitter at  $(\ell + 1)$  for an increasing trend in jitter (see Figure 3)
    % Calculate the jitter metric for loss of lock detection (i.e., the mean of bounds, as discussed in Section 3)

    % Calculation of the total a priori and a posteriori TF jitters
    if(loop_count == 0.1) % Executed only once for a given TF model
        % Consider appropriate H, W and K matrices for the TF model, which would last for  $T_{sub}(tf\_index)$ 
        % Using Algorithm 1, calculate the process and measurement noise BWs for the TFs in Equations 18 and 19
    end
    if(loop_count  $\sim$   $T_{sub}(tf\_index)$ )
        loop_count = loop_count + 0.1; % Increment the loop_count for the duration of  $T_{sub}(tf\_index)$  ( $\geq 0.1$ )
    else
        loop_count = 0.1; % Reset to 0.1 to re-calculate the BWs as a new TF model would start in the next iteration
        tf_index = tf_index + 1; % Increment tf_index by one to point to the next TF model
    end
end

```

```
% For the dynamic stress error at  $\ell$ , determine the impulse response of  $(z\mathbf{I} - (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_q\mathbf{H}_q)\mathbf{F})^{-1}$  after 0.1 s due to  
%  $\Delta z_{dyn, tf, \ell-1}^+$  in Equation 27 (and similarly due to  $\Delta z_{dyn, tf, \ell-1}^-$  in Equation 28). Use the Matlab function,  
% 'impz', for this purpose  
% Determine the step response of  $(z\mathbf{I} - (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_q\mathbf{H}_q)\mathbf{F})^{-1}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_q\mathbf{H}_q)$  after 0.1 s due to  $\mathbf{B}_{u_{jerk}, \ell-1}$  in Equation 27  
% (and similarly in Equation 28), and add it to the corresponding impulse response to find the dynamic stress error  
% Use Equations 22, 23, 29 and 30 to calculate the total a posteriori TF jitter. Similarly, calculate the a priori TF jitter  
end
```